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The structure of political speech

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In the current geopolitical situation and post-information society, political discourse is invariably at the center of many researches. There are a lot of scientific discussions about the conceptual aspects of political discourse as a complex, multidimensional phenomenon, which is peculiar to different sciences. The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language proposes the following definition of the political discourse: Political discourse is a thematically defined text, which is conceived and intended as a whole and completed, but considered in the communication situation in which it unfolds.

Political discourse is a text defined by the subject of affirmation and expression of interests of political subjects in the process of their activity, struggle for political power, and considered in the situation of appropriate communication. At the same time, we can define politics as a system of relations between people, who operate in various government institutions in order to get benefits from mutual contacts and redistribution of power resources. The current understanding of politics is defined by the intensity of the struggle for power as the central motive for political activity.

There are following essential characteristics of political discourse:

- 1) thematic fronting of the text, its determination of the topic;
- 2) affirmation of interests of political subjects, struggle for political power as the main intention of political discourse;
- 3) presence of a communication situation, in which the peculiarities of the genre of political discourse are manifested.

Political activity can be defined as a kind of social activity which is characterized by the usage of political power and aimed at making certain decisions.

To successfully achieve its intention, the addressee-politician must anticipate people's reactions, this allows them to properly construct the composition of the discourse, take into account the type of information and the evaluation aspect. A politician who wants to achieve the desired pragmatic effect should carefully consider the composition of the speech and its content. It is true that formulating a specific statement, the addressee politician should solve at the same time the problems of building a model of the listener, modeling their own relationship with the audience and predicting its reactions to achieve a communicative effect.

Political language is a special subsystem of the national language, designed for political communication and propaganda of certain ideas, emotional impact on the citizens of the country. Politicians encourage the audience to take political actions, to develop public consensus, make and substantiate socio-

political decisions. In political communication, the sign of communicative reality is a political speech, which is perceived by the electorate and gives the opportunity to form the image of the politicians.

Modern studies of political leaders' speeches are presented by two methods: discourse analysis (the widest possible research of the paradigm) and semiotic analysis (narrower approach, which doesn't take into account the socio-historical conditions the object of analysis operates in, but focuses only on characteristics of the speeches).

By the term "structure" we mean the content – the way, in which the information is arranged in a specific sequence, which is followed throughout the speech. In addition, the specified element is divided into separate parts, which are logically interconnected and allow audience to understand the presented material and understand it. Thus, the composition is the inner "part" of speech that a speechwriter builds by adhering certain rules, strategies and techniques to make it sound most effectively and make impression. And only when this task is completed, then the speaker, relying on such "backbone" reproduces all ideas and considerations consistently and systematically.

Traditionally, the composition of speech is divided into three parts:

- 1) introduction;
- 2) main part;
- 3) ending.

These parts are called the functional structure components of the speech and the speaker does different tasks in each of them. In the first part he greets, establishes contact with the audience and announces the topic, the purpose of the speech, raises a number of issues for further analysis, interests the audience, assures that people can trust him or her, and wins general attention. Besides, the introduction can include additional elements: appreciations and words of gratitude to the listeners, compliments and establishment of the trust.

Introduction to political speech is one of the most important elements and it defines how successful a speech will be and set the high standard for the speaker. A lot of researches showed that after meeting or listening to the speech, watching the game, the brightest moments, which people remember, are the beginning and the end of the speech. The introduction helps to set contact with people. This element is an important aspect of speech because, for example, expressing gratitude at the event is essential, especially when the audience is waiting for it.

Certain problems and issues usually are revealed in details, discussed and supported by arguments or facts in the main part. The task of the main part is to reveal the topic, present your opinions, support them with evidence and prepare the audience for the conclusion. If it is enough to declare a problem in the introduction, it is necessary to make a decision in this part.

In order to organize all the information and trace the thoughts of the speaker, there is a smaller, informative, semantic unit which is called

“microtheme”. Microtheme – a complete in its content and structure fragment of language, which includes individual judgments obtained as a result of the division of the thesis, and arguments for their defense. The scope of the microtheme is not limited, the division into microthemes may not coincide with the division into sentences or paragraphs (for example, one microtheme may cover more than 5 paragraphs). Each microtheme usually has a construction similar to logical reasoning and consists of 3 parts: judgment, arguments, ending. And such a construction is truly reasonable, because every statement of the speaker must be supported by arguments.

In the end the speaker summarizes the opened topic, comes to a certain conclusion, over the idea and conversely, leaves for people with their own thoughts (there are cases when the last part is absent or not expressed at all). The main task of the end is to reinforce everything said before. However, it is necessary to strengthen and at the same time to enclose in the conclusion the main thesis of performance with which the audience will finish listening of reading the speech. A well-formed conclusion will be stored in the memory of the recipients for a long time, especially if it summarizes everything what has been said before.

Thus, the structure of political speech consists of individual details, which can be combined into one mechanism and in the hands of the skillful speaker turn into powerful speech. Political discourse is primarily studied within the framework of political communication. It is a specific manifestation of political communication, which involves the actualization of a political text in a communicative act of interaction between a political subjects (politics, political force, power) and political objects (audience, electorate, voters). It is characterized by informative component and actualization of mass media as a channel of communication, distancing and authoritarianism. An essential feature of discourse, understood in a broad sense, is its correlation with specific participants in the act (speaker and listener), as well as with the communicative intention of the speaker to influence the listener in some way. Ritual political discourse is produced on behalf of specific politicians, but the factors of the speaker and the author do not coincide; implemented in written and oral forms; preferably mass-addressed; contributes to the creation and maintenance of political image; mediated mainly through television, the Internet and articles in various newspapers.

The role of political speech is to achieve a distribution of forces in the process of struggle for power. Political speech is the main manipulative tool in political sphere and politicians use different various argumentative models, which affect the feelings of listeners, not their minds and these language tools should be reflected in translation. We have learned the structure of the main kinds of the speeches and what all of them usually consist of.